

Effect of Time Management Training on Academic Task Procrastination of Secondary School Students in Onitsha Local Government Area of Anambra State

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Abstract

Procrastination is a behavioural condition that causes major scholastic difficulties for all people, particularly students and teachers in a school setting. This study investigated the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of secondary school students in Onitsha North local government area of Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi experimental non-randomized pre-test and post-test, control group design was used for the study. Sample size of 580, SS 11 and J.SS 11, male and female secondary school students were purposively drawn from seven co-educational secondary schools with population size of 3550. The instrument for data collection was Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS). Mean was used to answer the research Questions while Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the null hypotheses. Findings of the study revealed among others that time management training was effective in reducing academic task procrastination among secondary school students. The study further showed that the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination was significant. Based on the findings, of the study, the following recommendations were made, among others: that guidance counsellor should start early to adopt the use of time management training in the reduction of academic task procrastination of secondary school students. Practicing counsellors should also make use of the time management training in counselling students towards reducing their academic task procrastination.

Key words: Time management, Training, Academic task, Procrastination, Students

Introduction

Students have the tendency to put off tasks that they must complete in order to enhance their lives and achieve success. Most of the time, they do not effectively manage their time and instead misuse it by doing things that are unrelated to achieving academic and life goals and objectives; they prefer to waste time on simple and pleasurable activities over more important tasks and activities that will bring success and meaning to their lives. Most of the time, this behavior leads to them failing to meet critical goals and

later regretting it. Procrastination is the term used to describe the act of deferring or postponing activities, and it is also used to describe the delay in scholastic tasks.

Academic task procrastination is the act of unnecessarily delaying or postponing academic tasks to the point of subjective discomfort, which is all too common. Academic task procrastination, according to Ellis and Knaus (2014), is defined as the desire to postpone an activity, the commitment to do it later, and the use of excuses to explain the delay and escape guilt. According to Ellis and Knaus, roughly 95 percent of college students procrastinate on academic tasks, resulting in poor academic performance, such as bad marks and course withdrawal. Academic task procrastination, according to Glick, Semb, and Spencer (2015), can stem from study habits such as last-minute studying.

Academic task Procrastination is widely regarded as a maladaptive behaviour that obstructs successful academic experiences. Academic task procrastination has been connected to a variety of negative academic behaviours, according to Eerde (2013), including missing or late assignments, a reduction in task preparation time, and quitting studying. Academic task procrastination is a common occurrence, particularly among secondary school students, due to the relatively flexible learning environment. According to some studies, approximately 70% of secondary school students consider themselves procrastinators, and similar reports can be found all over the world (Argumedo, Diaz-Morales, Ferrari & O'Callaghan, 2017; Klassen 2010; Seo, 2011).

According to Hopes, Burns, Hayes, Herbert, and Winner, academic task procrastination is connected to low academic accomplishment (2010). Hopes, Burns, Hayes, Herbert, and Winner described procrastination as a phenomena in which a person fails to complete a task or takes a lengthy time or delays in doing so. Procrastination can occur all the way up to the "last minute" before a deadline. Personal difficulties (bringing up a stressful topic with a relationship), health issues (going to the doctor or dentist late), home care issues (repairing a roof leak), and academic tasks/work responsibilities are all examples of things people may put off.

Academic task procrastination can lead to feelings of guilt, inadequacy, depression, stress, self-doubt and failure in examination. A tendency to procrastinate is almost universal among secondary school students. When task and assignments are giving to students, many do not get around to signing up on time (Dennis, 2010). Sdorow (2017) noted that academic task procrastination can also be as a result of irrational cognition, evasiveness of task, low self-esteem, delayed study behaviour, time mismanagement, complex interaction of behaviour of cognition and affective component. The tendency to engage in all these maladaptive behaviour in school is called academic task procrastination. In school setting, the delay in performing activities is known as academic task procrastination, also when students do not do their academic work on time, it is also referred to academic task procrastination.

Academic task procrastination is a type of procrastination that occurs in academic environments. It is understanding that one must complete an academic task or activity, such as writing a term paper, studying for exams, completing a school-related project, or completing weekly reading assignments, but failing to inspire oneself to do so within the specified time period for one reason or another (Ackerman & Gross, 2015). Academic task procrastination can be characterized as the delay of academic tasks to the point when optimal performance becomes highly unlikely, resulting in a condition of psychological distress (Ellis & Knaus, 2014; Ferrari, Johnson & McCown, 2016). Academic task procrastination can also be described as any academic task that is postponed or avoided as a result of a misalignment of intent and actual behavior that has a negative impact on the procrastinator. Academic task procrastination is a type of situational procrastination that has been defined as behavior associated with a specific task (Harris & Sutton, 2015).

As a result, it appears that college students are increasingly delaying academic assignments to the point where they are experiencing significant anxiety and receiving poor grades.

According to Solomon, Rothblum, and Murakami (2016), a high level of academic task procrastination is associated with lower grades, and even when procrastination does not result in failure, it can cause a lot of suffering because it pushes work to the last minute, causing the procrastinator to work under pressure, skip classes, give false excuses for late work, and feel ashamed of their last minute work. As a result, for the sake of this study, academic task procrastination is defined as the deliberate postponement of the start and/or completion of an overt or covert act that is frequently accompanied by subjective unpleasantness. It refers to consciously delaying a planned course of action in the face possible failure.

Time management therefore could be seen as one of the biggest challenge of students, especially those in the secondary schools. Time management training can be defined as training in having an ability to consciously control activities and behaviour so as to maximize one's available time (Mish, 2014). According to Jeff, Karin and Robert (2017), it is the act or process of training on planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency or productivity. It can thus be viewed as a tool with which one can build a greater life, marked by high achievement and a tremendous feeling of satisfaction and accomplishment. It can also be looked upon as a vehicle that can carry one from where one is, to where one wants to be. In the context of this study, the researcher defines time management as the art of setting a goal, with the planner and following it sequentially in order to achieve the target. Time management is the art of arranging, organizing, scheduling and budgeting ones time for the purpose of generating more effective work, and achieving more productive.

Time management may be aided by a range of skills, tools, and techniques used to manage time when accomplishing specific tasks, projects, and goals complying within a due date. Initially, time management applies to only business or work activities, but eventually the term broadened to include personal activities as well. A time management system is a designed combination of processes, tools, techniques, and methods. Time management training is usually a necessity in any project development both academics and non-academics as it determines the project completion time and scope (Myers, 2015). A formal time schedule can do much to prevent procrastination, maintain motivation in school and makes one to be disciplined.

When one develops the discipline of time management, one could simultaneously develop many of the other habits that lead to high achievement, wealth and success in every part of one's life. However, several factors have been identified as causes of poor time management which sometime lead to academic procrastination. Morakinyo (2013) believed that the falling level of academic task performance is attributable to teachers' non-use of verbal reinforcement strategy and lack of proper time management training. Welsh (2017) also found that the attitude of some teachers to their jobs, poor teaching methods and the likes, influence students' academic task procrastination. The blame of poor academic task procrastination among secondary school students could be attributed to a variety of factors such as student's inability to manage their time, peer influence, poor cognition, family factors, Parental influence, teacher's attitude and likes.

However, despite numerous effort made by the previous researchers in finding a lasting solution to the problem of academic task procrastination, among secondary school students, the problems no doubts still posed serious challenges to guidance counsellors, teachers and other professionals in seeing that an effective solution to the problem be realized since it affects both male and females. Gender based studies

on academic task procrastination demonstrated that female students procrastinate more frequently in their academic task (Rodarte – Luna & Sherry, 2017) while some studies proved a different attitude depicting that academic task procrastination is common among male students (Arif, Muneer, Noor & Khan, 2016; Balkis & Duru, 2016,). Findings of the study showed that males are more intended to procrastinate in academic task than females. On the other hand, another group of studies reported that gender has no effect on the academic task procrastinate behavior (Okun, 2011). Ferrari and Ozer (2011) in that regard found no significant difference between male and female students on academic task procrastination, to control and manage academic task procrastination, students must learn to restructure their cognition and manage their time effectively.

Although research efforts has been made to finding a way of dealing with the problem of students' academic task procrastination, so that students can face and execute their academic tasks as and when due, the efforts seem not to have made much impact. One would easily observe that students in Anambra state secondary schools are still languishing in their academic task procrastination; they still voluntarily delay an intended course of action despite expecting to be worst off by the delay. This has necessitated this study which is being carried out to investigate the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination to reduce academic task procrastination and subsequently enhance performance among

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pre-test and post-test scores?
2. What is the difference in the effects of time management training on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of secondary school students when compared with conventional counselling using their pre-test and post-test scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the effects of time management training on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores.

Method

This study adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test control group design. It is a type of study that seeks to determine the effect of a treatment paradigm on a non-randomised sample. The sample size for the study was 580 male and female students in JS 11 and SS 11. The sample size was drawn from the population of 3550 respondents with high procrastination scores in the coeducational secondary schools in Onitsha North local government area, from which three schools with highest number of respondents identified as academic task procrastinators were purposively selected.

The instrument that was used for assessment is Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS). Tuckman developed the Procrastination Scale (PS) in 1991. The instrument was designed to measure task avoidance to academic activities. It is self-report instrument which identifies academic procrastinators, through measuring of procrastination tendencies. The Procrastination Scale (PS) consists of 16-items which are

scored on a four-point Likert scale (i.e. 1 = that's me for sure, 2 = that's my tendency, 3 = that's not my tendency, 4 = that's not me for sure). The internal consistency reliability estimate of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method and was found to be 0.82. In order to determine the stability of the instrument over time, a test retest analysis was done using Pearson correlation method, this was necessary since the same instrument was reshuffled and used for pre-test and post-test. All the students from the three secondary schools chosen from all the coeducational secondary schools were given the Tuckman procrastination scale to fill. Copies of the instrument were given to students and then retrieved from the students immediately they finished responding to it and was then handed over to the researcher for collation and scoring according to the specification on the Tuckman procrastination scale manual. The completed copies of the instruments were scored following the scoring instructions provided in the manual. Responses to the 16 individual items were summed to create an overall score for the scale. Scores on the 16-item Tuckman (1991) scale ranged from 16-63. Scores that are above the norm 40.0 were seen as indicative of procrastination. The scores were collated and analysed using SPSS analysis. The data relating to the research questions were analysed using the mean. The data relating to the null hypotheses were analysed using the Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA). The analysed data were interpreted. Scores that are below the norm 39.5 - 40.0 showed that the technique was effective, while scores that are above the norm show that the technique was not effective.

Results

Data collected from the field for this study were analysed and the summaries were presented in tables to highlight the findings as follows:

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest academic task procrastination mean scores of students treated with time management technique and those treated with conventional counselling (Norm = 40)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Time management Tech.	193	55.59	26.61	28.98	Effective
Conventional Counselling	188	55.21	43.85	11.36	

Table 1 reveals that the students treated with time management technique had pretest mean score of 55.59 and posttest mean score of 26.61 with lost mean 28.98 in their academic task procrastination, while those in the control group who received conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 55.21 and posttest mean score of 43.85 with lost mean 11.36. With posttest mean score of 26.61 which is below the norm of 40.00 time management technique is effective in reducing academic task procrastination among secondary school students.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest academic task procrastination mean scores of male and female students treated with time management technique

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Male	108	54.90	24.28	30.62	More Effective
Female	85	56.47	29.58	26.89	

Table 2 indicates that male students treated with time management technique had pretest mean score of 54.90 and posttest mean score of 24.28 with lost mean 30.62 in their academic task procrastination, while the female students treated with the technique had pretest mean score of 56.47 and posttest mean score of 29.58 with lost mean 26.89. With lost mean of 30.62 as against 26.89 for male and female students

respectively, time management technique is more effective in reducing academic task procrastination of male secondary school students.

Table 3: ANCOVA on the effect of time management technique on academic task procrastination of secondary school students when compared with those who received conventional counselling

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	28304.0052		14152.003			
Intercept	1983.509	1	1983.509			
PRETEST	0.0051		0.005			
METHODS	28222.3481		28222.348	916.524	.000	S
Error	11639.680	378	30.793			
Total	509824.000	381				
Corrected Total	39943.685	380				

Table 3 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 380df denominator, the calculated F is 916.52 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of time management technique on the academic task procrastination of secondary school students is significant.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the effectiveness of time management technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	1403.2434		350.811			
Intercept	626.2641		626.264			
PRETEST	0.6911		0.691			
GENDER	1211.118	1	1211.11875	75.081	.000	S
Error	032.612	188	16.131			
Total	141112.000	193				
Corrected Total	4435.855	192				

Table 4 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 192df denominator, the calculated F is 75.08 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the fifth null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effectiveness of time management technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students differ significantly.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that time management training was effective in reducing academic task procrastination of secondary school students. The findings further showed that the effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of secondary school students was significant. What these means is that the outcome of time management training on secondary school students academic task procrastination was effective, hence the technique was able to reduce students' academic task procrastination. The finding of the study is in agreement with Nadinloyi, Hajloo, Garamaleki and Sadeghi (2013) in Cleavarance whose study revealed that time management training was efficacious in reducing academic task procrastination among secondary school students. The finding is also in line with the work

of Hamzah, Lucky and Joader (2014) who conducted a study on the effects of time management training on adolescents' self-esteem in Lagos State secondary schools. The result showed time management training and assertiveness were effective in managing adolescents' self-esteem. The result was also in line with the study of Okun (2011) whose study examined efficacy of time management training techniques on improving coping skills of students in psychology set up. The findings revealed that the treatment group reported significantly greater improvement than the control group for secondary outcomes.

The possible reasons for these findings could be linked to the idea that completing the time management training program was helpful for students to understand time management skills and how to apply it practically, learn the skills necessary for formulating and maintaining good time management skills. For instance, time management training is based on understanding that time is fixed and if wasted cannot be recovered. Another possible explanation for the obtained results is that the students who had participated in the program would have become more successful in utilization of their time in the reduction of academic task procrastination. The time management training possibly provided students with opportunity to manage, keep a to do list, prioritise, organize, scale their activities, become a master of their own, schedule its duties and project planning, as a result increasing appropriate time management behaviour.

The result reveals that the effect of time management training technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students differ significantly. The findings of this study is in agreement with the findings of Nwakoby (2010) whose study affirmed that female in school adolescent performed slightly higher than the male in school adolescent academically. This could be attributed to the fact that both genders were attentive and enthusiastic about the study therefore the significant effect of time management training was not due to gender. Jackson (2015) in his study observe no difference based on gender, noting that female spend significantly more time working on home work than male students. Time management skills help students to independently plan, monitor and access self, time management was not gender dependant.

The effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students differ significantly, it is therefore opined that both males and females should be given time management training to help them in planning and managing themselves and for enhanced academic performance since the training is beneficial to both group. There is an indication that both male and female students gained from the time management training given to them and were able to make adjustment in their time management. This helped them in managing their academic task and avoiding procrastination.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that time management training have significant effect on the academic task procrastination of secondary school students. Hence, it was effective in reduction of the students' academic task procrastination. The study also concluded that time management training was more effective reducing academic procrastination of male secondary school students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Since time management technique was effective on students' task procrastination in secondary schools, counsellors should employ the use of the technique ain training to reduce academic task procrastination of secondary school students.
2. School administrators should work towards organizing training programmes for guidance counsellor in schools on these two factors for their effective use in other to reduce the spirally accelerated effects of academic task procrastination of secondary school students.

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